

Bound State Quantum Mechanics as a Statistical Theory

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 21, 2020

In this note, we try to develop bound state quantum mechanics directly from statistical arguments. The key idea, we argue, is that a statistical treatment of a system considers “free particles” together with a stochastic equilibrium driving mechanism. If an acceleration driving potential exists (as in classical statistical mechanics), it alters the results, but does not change the main scenario of free particles interacting through a stochastic mechanism at a point because one does not follow particles in time, noting how they accelerate as they travel. (For example, a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas distribution is based on two body elastic scattering whether there is a potential or not. The potential affects the density, but not the relative momentum probabilities at any x .) For the quantum case, the potential $V(x)$ is the stochastic equilibrium driver, but on average kinetic energy plus potential must equal total energy. Again, one does not follow the quantum particle in time trying to see if or how it accelerates.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics seems to be based on the idea that at any point x (1-dimension) there exists a real, positive probability to have a certain momentum (whether there is a potential or not). Thus, one does not think in terms of particle paths and acceleration, but rather in terms of probability as a function of p and x for a free particle. In other words, $C \exp(-pp/2mT + V(x)/T)$ is the probability of finding a free particle with momentum p at x . Given a potential, the particle “accelerates”, but one does not follow this acceleration. One is only interested in p and x which characterize a free particle.

The Quantum Bound State

Consider a quantum bound state with one particle. In such a case, one may mimic classical statistical mechanics and consider probabilities for free particles as a function of p and x i.e. $g(p,x)$. In other words, there is a momentum distribution at each x (due to a stochastic potential which is $V(x)$ on average). Unlike classical statistical mechanics, the average kinetic energy at each x must satisfy:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Thus, the constraint is applied after one has the form of $g(p,x)$. In classical statistical mechanics, the stochastic driver of equilibrium i.e. elastic scattering determines the form of $g(p,x)$ i.e. $f(p_1)f(p_2)=f(p_3)f(p_4)$ or $\ln(f(p_1))+\ln(f(p_2))=\ln(f(p_3)) + \ln(f(p_4))$ which is equated to kinetic energy conservation.

$g(p,x)$ must be a function of both p and x , otherwise one could not have $KE_{ave}(x)$ change with x .

The assumption that $g(p,x)$ represents “free particles”, however, introduces further restrictions. The free particle assumption is strictly a statistical notion as one does not follow the acceleration of particles either in quantum mechanics or classical statistical mechanics.

In classical statistical mechanics, a free particle (no potential) should have equal probability to be at any x . In quantum mechanics, there is a potential which suggests a spatial density according to classical statistical mechanics. Nevertheless, the idea of statistics seems to be that one does not follow acceleration and deals with a stochastic interaction mechanism and free particles at each x . It is a stochastic hit from a potential which changes a particle from momentum p_1 to p_2 . If this stochastic hit does not occur, the particle moves as a free particle. This seems to be a key idea (or assumption). Given that a momentum distribution exists at each x , one may obtain $g(p,x)$ for a particular p at each x and find a function in x for the probability of p .

If $g(p,x)$ for the quantum bound state represents a free particle, it should be identical for all x . It, however, cannot be a constant in x as noted above ($KE_{ave}(x)$ must change in x). The closest function which treats all x points in the same manner is a periodic one. A real periodic function for $g(p,x)$ (p fixed) has different values within its wavelength (period). It is not possible in this case for probability to appear and vanish with x . Thus, it seems one must introduce two channels, each with a periodic function. This leads to the idea of the possible solution:

$$g(p,x) = \exp(i f(p)x) \quad ((2))$$

The two channels being $\cos(f(p)x)$ and $i \sin(f(p)x)$ such that the modulus of probability (conditional probability) is conserved. As a result, conditional probability is complex.

We have made arguments in previous notes regarding the form of $f(p)$. If one uses the idea of a Lorentz invariant then $px-Et$ is a candidate. If one uses the idea of momentum as carrying probability flux, then $d/dx g(p,x)$ proportional to p is a possible solution and also leads to $f(p)=p$.

The above scenario, based on ideas of statistics, leads, we argue, to a complex conditional probability which is also periodic and of the form $\exp(ipx)$. For a momentum distribution at x one has: $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ (the wavefunction). In addition, the above statistical ideas lead directly to interference of $\exp(ipx)$ terms because $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ may be positive or negative. No physical assumptions have been introduced to account for a complex probability or interference.

Change in Potential Energy

As shown in ((1)), $KE_{ave}(x)$ must change from x to $x+dx$ to counter $V(x)$ changes in order that E remain constant. The fact that one postulates a momentum distribution at x already suggests a stochastic potential must be present in the problem, otherwise one would have a single momentum. A stochastic potential also suggests the problem is handled in a statistical manner, i.e. one does not follow the particle in time as it accelerates. As a result, the distribution at each x is one of “free particles”. Since one may consider a distribution at each x , it is as if one has a

continuous free particle conditional probability i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, due to statistical considerations discussed above.

We wish to point out that even though $K_{Eave}(x)$ changes with x as a classical value, each p contribution does not. In other words:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \frac{\sum_p p p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)}{W} \right\} - \left[\frac{\sum_p a(p) p p/2m \exp(ipx)}{W} \right] \frac{d}{dx} \ln W = \frac{d}{dx} (-dV/dx) \quad (3)$$

If one considers Newton's law for a single p , then:

$$F dx = p/m dp/dx = p/m a(p) ip \exp(ipx) \quad (4)$$

which is not the case in quantum mechanics.

Thus, a statistical theory is developed which only yields Newton's law for average kinetic energy.

Conclusion

Quantum mechanics includes unusual complex wavefunctions and interference which are unusual from the point of view of classical physics. In this note, we try to develop bound state quantum mechanics strictly from the point of view of statistics. In other words, we consider a momentum distribution of free particles at each x point (just as in classical statistical mechanics). In classical statistical mechanics with a potential $V(x)$, the particles accelerate at each x , but this does not enter into the equations for two body scattering at each x , i.e. into the stochastic driver of equilibrium. (One introduces it by arguing that $.5 m v_1 v_1 = .5 m v v + V(x)$ i.e. a particular kinetic energy with v_1 and no potential is created by a kinetic v and a potential $V(x)$).

Using the idea of a free particle momentum distribution and stochastic hits from a potential, we argue that it follows that free particle relative conditional probability should be of the form $\exp(ipx)$ leading to $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. Thus, the unusual complex wavefunction and ideas of interference seem to follow directly as consequences of the idea of an ensemble of free quantum particles i.e. a statistical solution of a quantum bound problem.